

SPECIAL ISSUE: Reflections and Learnings for a Post-War Urban Planning

Gender perspective on urban planning amidst European integration and post-conflict impact: The Ukrainian case

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Abstract

In post-conflict societies, urban development efforts typically prioritise reconstruction and accessibility. This paper examines the potential for integrating gender-responsive approaches into urban planning in Ukraine, where the priorities of post-war reconstruction intersect with the processes of European integration. While EU support and funding predominantly focus on the creation of barrier-free environments, European integration has also contributed to the establishment of institutional mechanisms and cultural foundations for advancing gender equality. The article critically evaluates whether the simultaneous processes of post-war reconstruction, societal transformation, and European integration present a "window of opportunity" for embedding gender mainstreaming in urban planning, or whether the pressing imperative of developing barrier-free environments will remain the dominant priority in the foreseeable future.

Keywords

urban planning, barrier-free environment, gender, post-conflict reconstruction, post-war reconstruction, EU

Introduction

Global demographic trends demonstrate a fundamental transformation in the patterns of human settlement, whereby the millennia-long predominance of rural communities has yielded to urbanisation, a process that has intensified markedly in recent decades. This large-scale migration towards urban centres has resulted in more than 4 billion people now residing in urbanised areas (Ritchie et al., 2024). Within this context, urban planning has emerged as a

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critical instrument for ensuring quality of life, wherein it not only determines the spatial organisation of cities but also exerts considerable influence over social cohesion, economic opportunities, environmental sustainability and the security of urban communities (Duque & Panagopoulos, 2010; Adeloje & Rustum, 2011; Watson, 2009; Koomen & Diogo, 2015; Asarpota & Nadin, 2020; Teklemariam, 2022).

The asymmetrical distribution of urban infrastructure, transport accessibility and quality public spaces serves to exacerbate social inequality and the marginalisation of vulnerable populations (Derr et al., 2013; Whiston Spirn, 2005). Moreover, the urban environment presents distinct barriers for women, whose needs have historically been overlooked in urban planning processes (Wekerle, 1980).

The matter of gender policy development acquired international significance following the Fourth World Conference on Women in Beijing in 1995 (Haysom, 1996) This conference culminated in the Beijing Platform for Action, which established gender mainstreaming as the fundamental approach towards addressing gender inequality through the systematic incorporation of gender perspectives across all policies and programmes (United Nations, 1995). The subsequent United Nations Conference on Human Settlements (Habitat II) in 1996 produced the Habitat Agenda, wherein gender mainstreaming was established as the key mechanism for addressing the distinct needs of women and men in human settlement development whilst promoting women's equitable participation in planning and decision-making processes (UN-Habitat, 2012).

The evolution of gender equality policy within the European Union has witnessed significant institutional developments, progressing from the establishment of equality and non-discrimination principles in the 1997 Amsterdam Treaty to the recognition of gender equality as a fundamental value in the 2007 Lisbon Treaty (Fiig, 2020). Indeed, the European Union has established itself as the principal regional agent for implementing gender mainstreaming, adapting global principles to the particular social, economic and political contexts of both member states (Booth & Bennett, 2002; Jacquot, 2015; Elgström, 2017) and candidate countries (Stivachtis & Georgakis, 2011; Ristova-Aasterud, 2017).

Of particular scholarly interest is the examination of how countries' trajectories towards European integration influence the development of gender-sensitive and gender-responsive approaches within urban planning frameworks. Furthermore, the challenge of reconciling these approaches with the urgent imperatives of post-conflict urban reconstruction warrants specific academic attention.

Military conflicts invariably result in extensive destruction of urban infrastructure, necessitating immediate restoration to address fundamental population needs (McKellar, 2014;

Sowers & Weinthal, 2021; Haque et al., 2022). The pressing requirement for rapid housing stock restoration to accommodate internally displaced persons and those whose dwellings have been destroyed assumes particular urgency (Viatkin & Kolodezny, 2023). Moreover, military actions significantly deteriorate living conditions for elderly populations (Fočić, 2017) and persons with disabilities (Zaviršek & Cox, 2024), whose numbers demonstrate marked increases during conflict periods (Baskaran, 2017; Shahabi et al., 2021). Under such circumstances, the creation of barrier-free environments for individuals with reduced mobility emerges as a priority (Yaroshenko et al., 2022). Consequently, one observes that in the process of addressing these fundamental population needs, the implementation of gender-responsive approaches to urban planning may be relegated to secondary consideration.

The contemporary situation in Ukraine presents a particularly compelling case study, owing to an unprecedented convergence of factors: European integration aspirations, requirements for extensive post-conflict reconstruction, substantial international support, and profound demographic transformations. This unique concatenation of circumstances raises a critical question for scholarly examination: might this situation present a 'window of opportunity' for the implementation of gender-responsive approaches in urban planning, or, conversely, does the imperative to address immediate challenges render such implementation substantially more complex? This question assumes particular significance when one considers the broader implications for post-conflict urban development.

Prospects for Gender Integration in Urban Planning of Central and Eastern European Countries: Historical and Political Context

To comprehend the contemporary challenges of urban planning in Central and Eastern European countries, it is essential to examine their historical context. During the Soviet period, urban planning in Ukraine constituted an integral component of the Soviet Union's overarching policy, which emphasised standardisation, centralised control, and rapid construction of residential and industrial facilities (Mezentsev et al., 2023; Mariotti & Leetmaa, 2023). Cities were planned and developed in accordance with unified standards, with particular emphasis on functionality that aligned with the USSR's economic objectives (Zile, 1963). The resulting homogeneous urban environment failed to ensure adequate levels of comfort and aesthetic quality, whilst neglecting residents' individual needs (Bunkse, 1979). Despite proclaimed equality, the Soviet approach to urban planning disregarded both the specific requirements of persons with disabilities (Phillips, 2009) and the needs of women and families with multiple children (Attwood, 2010). Similar circumstances prevailed throughout socialist European countries, where modernised and ostensibly egalitarian urban planning remained detached from

genuine social needs and overlooked the spatial requirements of diverse social groups (Pajvančić-Cizelj & Hjuson, 2018).

Following the 1989 political transformations, the political elites of Central and Eastern European countries rejected state regulation as a symbol of socialism, favoring private interests instead. This shift resulted in private developers gaining substantial influence over urban development. Urban planners faced a legitimacy crisis, which complicated the development of coherent urban development strategies. These factors led to socio-spatial stratification and new planning challenges (Stanilov, 2007).

A new phase in urban planning development commenced with European integration processes. Transition countries sought pathways to overcome crises precipitated by their shift towards market economies, with the majority achieving a measure of institutional stability post-2000. In Central European and Baltic countries that acquired EU membership in 2004, prospects for sustainable urban development improved markedly, accompanied by successful instances of enhanced citizen participation in planning processes (Hirt & Stanilov, 2009). European financing instruments, legal frameworks, and approaches to social inclusivity and sustainable development contributed substantially to improving quality of life in these countries' urban centres (Ciesiółka & Burov, 2021).

Nevertheless, the EU's role in shaping urban policy exhibits certain limitations. Whilst the EU maintains a significant position in establishing the pan-European agenda, it lacks direct legislative authority in urban policy and development, as these matters remain under the immediate jurisdiction of member states' national governments. Urban policy development within the EU framework has proceeded through the implementation of non-binding political instruments, which frequently overlooked the integration of gender approaches (De Gregorio Hurtado, 2020). This circumstance significantly diminishes the likelihood of gender mainstreaming implementation in urban planning at both national and municipal levels (Donati & Rodríguez-García, 2024).

A crucial step towards fostering gender equality at the local level was initiated through a 'bottom-up' approach: the European Charter for Equality of Women and Men in Local Life, established in 2006 by the Council of European Municipalities and Regions with support from the European Commission. The Charter emphasises the importance of incorporating gender considerations across all spheres of local policy, including urban planning (Council of European Municipalities and Regions, 2006). Whilst 2000 communities from 36 countries had signed the Charter as of January 2023 (Observatory of the European Charter, 2023a), the CEMR website, established to support Charter implementation, presents remarkably few successful examples

of signatories implementing gender approaches in urban planning (Observatory of the European Charter, 2023b).

To strengthen gender approach integration, the EU developed several targeted mechanisms. Notably, through specialised programmes such as URBAN and URBANA, the integration of gender-sensitive and gender-inclusive policies into member states' urban development projects was encouraged, yielding positive outcomes (Rodríguez-García & Donati, 2021). These and other programmes received funding through the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and European Social Fund (ESF), which maintain mandatory requirements to promote equality between women and men. Consequently, all programmes receiving EU funding must incorporate gender equality considerations (Wankiewicz, 2013).

Scholars observe that for effective outcomes, the 'top-down' gender mainstreaming strategy must be reinforced by national, regional, and local spatial strategies that incorporate specific gender equality objectives (Huning et al., 2019). Moreover, the successful implementation of gender mainstreaming or any other gender strategy necessitates not merely formal political and legal mechanisms, but also active participants committed to creating a gender-equitable society (Wankiewicz, 2013).

However, current trends in the region give rise to considerable concern. Recent developments in Central-Eastern European countries demonstrate various forms of gender policy dismantling, ranging from direct abolition to gradual erosion of implementation mechanisms (Krizsan & Roggeband, 2018). In Western Balkan countries pursuing European integration and formally adapting to EU policies (Nežirović et al., 2022), the implementation of gender-sensitive approaches to urban planning faces significant impediments due to weak local institutions and insufficient funding (Pajvančić-Cizelj & Hjuson, 2018).

Is there a window of opportunity for gender-responsive urban planning in Ukraine?

Initial urban development challenges: Post-Soviet context

The post-Soviet transformation period presented considerable challenges for Ukraine's urban development trajectory. Whilst numerous post-Soviet states managed to establish clear development paths, Ukraine found itself amongst those nations that failed to determine their political direction in a timely manner, thereby exacerbating existing economic and social challenges (Hirt & Stanilov, 2009). This indeterminacy precipitated pronounced socio-economic and spatial polarisation, which subsequently complicated the implementation of effective urban planning strategies. Indeed, whilst regions with high urbanisation levels successfully developed contemporary infrastructure and maintained quality urban environments, numerous other cities

confronted significant infrastructural deterioration and diminished access to fundamental services for substantial segments of the population (Mezentsev et al., 2015).

Evolution of the Ukraine's gender policy framework

To comprehend the prospects for gender-responsive planning in Ukraine, it is essential to first examine the evolution of the country's gender policy framework within the European integration context. This development process, shaped by EU policies and requirements, has established the institutional and cultural foundations upon which current urban planning initiatives must necessarily build.

Ukraine's trajectory towards European integration gained substantial momentum with the country's accession to the European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP) in 2004 (Smith, 2005). Within this framework, the EU-Ukraine Cooperation Council established the EU-Ukraine Action Plan (2005-2007), wherein gender equality emerged as a significant priority. Whilst the ENP endeavoured to foster stable relations between the EU and neighbouring countries whilst preventing further eastward expansion, it is noteworthy that the substantial requirements imposed upon neighbouring states lacked commensurate incentives from the EU. This imbalance arguably compromised the quality of reform implementation (Council of the European Union, 2005), particularly in the sphere of gender equality advancement.

The period following Ukraine's engagement with the ENP witnessed significant legislative developments in gender policy. A particularly noteworthy advancement occurred in 2005 with the adoption of the Law "On Ensuring Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" (Protosavitska, 2023). Subsequently, from 2006 onwards, the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine systematically approved state programmes aimed at ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2006, 2013, 2018a). Nevertheless, analysis of The Global Gender Gap Report data reveals a paradoxical deterioration in Ukraine's position in the global gender equality ranking between 2006 and 2008 (Hausmann et al., 2008)¹.

The signing of the EU-Ukraine Association Agreement in 2014, which entered into force in September 2017, marked a significant advancement in Ukraine's commitment to gender equality. This agreement necessitated the gradual approximation of Ukrainian legislation to EU standards, notably in ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men (European Union & Ukraine, 2014). From 2018 onwards, the Government's priority action plans systematically incorporated measures directed towards achieving gender equality (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2018b, 2018c).

¹ The country's position dropped from 48th place in 2006 to 57th place in 2007, and further declined to 62nd place in 2008.

Gender integration, as a principle of policy formation, resulted in the development of legislative acts that incorporated gender equality considerations into sectoral strategies and plans (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2017a, 2017b; Ministry of Finance of Ukraine, 2019). The Government Programme of Activities stipulated that the advancement of gender equality policy necessitates the implementation of European standards for women and men's equality through the modernisation of legislative frameworks, gender-legal expertise mechanisms, and statistical indicators (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2020b). An important step in institutional gender mainstreaming was taken in 2020, when the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine established a mandatory requirement for senior civil service candidates to demonstrate competence in gender impact assessment throughout the policy cycle, encompassing development, implementation, and evaluation phases (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2020c).

Sustainable Development Goals and urban development: Challenges of gender integration

The implementation of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into national legislation has emerged as another significant mechanism for addressing gender inequality in Ukraine. These goals, adopted at the 2015 UN Summit, represent a universal call to action for poverty reduction, environmental protection, and ensuring peace and prosperity by 2030 (President of Ukraine, 2019). The integration of SDGs into Ukrainian state policy warrants particular consideration within the European integration context, as these goals constitute a cornerstone of European policy, firmly embedded within European treaties and incorporated into key European Commission initiatives (Renda, 2017; Redek et al., 2020; Hametner & Kostetckaia, 2020). To align national legislation with EU requirements, Ukraine is implementing the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) for enterprises, with full adoption planned by 2030 (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2024a). The European Union actively supports Ukraine in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals through various programs and financial initiatives (Panov & Kushchak, 2021; Turchyn et al., 2022a, 2022b).

Of particular relevance to urban gender equality are SDG 5 (Gender Equality) and SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities). However, certain inconsistencies emerge between these goals at the implementation level. Notably, Goal 11 (specifically targets 11.2 and 11.7) categorises women alongside children, elderly people, and persons with disabilities as vulnerable groups. Conversely, components of Goal 5 advocate for women's equitable participation in social life, which, in the context of urban planning, would necessitate their inclusion as key agents of change in planning processes. There remains a critical necessity to strengthen the coherence between these goals at both policy formulation and implementation

levels, particularly to ensure women's substantive participation in urban development decision-making processes (East, 2022).

A critical examination of the national report Sustainable Development Goals: Ukraine' reveals significant limitations in its adaptation of global objectives. The document's presentation of the national SDG framework demonstrates a notable reduction in SDG 11 tasks, particularly concerning the omission of references to vulnerable groups, including women. Moreover, the adapted version of SDG 5 addresses only a limited scope of gender aspects compared to those established in the global SDG 5 framework (Ministry of Economic Development and Trade of Ukraine, 2017). This divergence between global objectives and national adaptation frameworks suggests the need for more comprehensive integration of gender considerations in Ukraine's.

Prioritising barrier-free environment over gender-responsive urban planning: The Impact of Biarritz Partnership²

Ukraine's accession to the Biarritz Partnership in 2020, an initiative led by G7 countries, marked a significant advancement in gender policy development (President of Ukraine, 2020). Whilst this initiative aims to consolidate international efforts towards achieving gender equality between women and men (G7 France, 2019), its implementation in Ukraine's urban development context manifested primarily through the development of barrier-free public spaces accessible to families with children and individuals with reduced mobility (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2020a).

The subsequent development and approval of the National Strategy for Creating a Barrier-Free Environment through 2030 has been explicitly positioned within Ukraine's European integration context (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2021a). As the President of Ukraine noted in his address, 'The approval of the National Strategy for creating a barrier-free space in Ukraine represents a significant step forward for the entire nation. This fundamental document advances our country's inclusivity whilst strengthening connections with European Union member states, where the principle of equal rights and opportunities underpins all governmental decisions' (Office of the President of Ukraine, 2021).

The Strategy places considerable emphasis on ensuring accessibility of physical environment and transport systems for persons with disabilities, elderly individuals, youth, women, parents with young children. It encompasses comprehensive measures, including:

- Modernisation of building codes to incorporate universal design principles;

² Although the Biarritz Partnership is not an EU initiative, its goals and principles align with European Union policies and values, therefore Ukraine's accession to it can logically be considered a consequence of European integration policy.

- Enhancement of transport infrastructure through installation of ramps, lifts, tactile guidance and information systems;
- Ensuring accessibility of parks, squares, public buildings and other urban infrastructure;
- Implementation of professional training programmes for architects, builders and urban planners;
- Integration of public participation in decision-making processes regarding barrier-free environment creation (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2021a).

To facilitate coordination among executive authorities regarding barrier-free space development and policy implementation, the government established the Barrier-Free Council. This body, chaired by the Prime Minister of Ukraine, includes high-ranking officials and notably the Government Commissioner for Gender Policy (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2021b).

Within the framework of implementing the National Strategy for Creating a Barrier-Free Environment through 2030, the government adopted an Action Plan for 2023-2024, establishing a comprehensive set of measures to ensure accessibility and inclusivity across various spheres of public life (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2023). The plan's effective implementation framework encompasses engagement of central and local executive authorities, civil society organisations, and international partners. The Ministry for Communities, Territories and Infrastructure Development of Ukraine oversees the monitoring process through a system of quarterly reporting and coordination between central and local authorities. Implementation progress and performance indicators are regularly published on official websites for public access (2024a).

As of August 2024, 364 territorial communities have incorporated barrier-free priorities into their strategies, local action plans, development programmes, and other strategic documents. The communities of Dnipropetrovsk, Lviv, Rivne, Cherkasy, and Odesa regions have shown notable initiative in advancing barrier-free policies (Ministry for Communities, Territories and Infrastructure Development of Ukraine, 2024b).

Post-war reconstruction and demographic challenges

Russia's full-scale invasion has precipitated substantial destruction of Ukraine's infrastructure and economy. As of January 2024, direct damage to infrastructure is estimated at approximately \$155 billion, with over 250,000 residential buildings damaged or destroyed. Direct losses to housing stock amount to \$58.9 billion, with the regions of Donetsk, Kyiv, Luhansk,

Kharkiv, Chernihiv, and Kherson sustaining the most significant damage (Kyiv School of Economics, 2024).

Should Ukraine's post-war urban reconstruction draw upon European best practices, an opportunity emerges to implement enhanced urban planning standards (Basysta & Smirnova, 2024). The European Union has actively engaged in developing and implementing Ukraine's reconstruction plans, positioning this as a key strategic priority. A significant milestone was reached in July 2022 with the Ukraine Recovery Conference in Lugano (Switzerland), which introduced the Ukraine Reconstruction Platform. The EU assumed the role of coordinator for this platform, integrating efforts of international partners, financial institutions, and the private sector for effective reconstruction (European Commission, 2022).

The reconstruction endeavour envisions mobilising over \$750 billion over the next decade (Fabbrini, 2023). Given that the primary reconstruction priorities encompass infrastructure and housing restoration, new safety standards, and the creation of inclusive and barrier-free environments, there exists an urgent necessity for developing new project documentation (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2023).

Ukraine's recovery process necessitates close collaboration with international partners, particularly through the Ukraine Facility initiative, a specialized European Union instrument designed to support Ukraine's recovery, reconstruction, and modernisation in response to Russian aggression. This programme allocates up to €50 billion in grants and loans for the period 2024-2027, including support for implementing key reforms on the path to EU membership (Fabbrini, 2023).

To secure this funding, Ukraine must implement the "Ukraine Plan" developed by the Cabinet of Ministers. Whilst this document references "gender equality"³ sixteen times, these references do not specifically address urban planning contexts. Instead, infrastructure restoration is primarily linked to barrier-free environment standards (Ministry of Economy of Ukraine, 2024).

The creation of a barrier-free environment has become increasingly critical for Ukraine, given the demographic crisis exacerbated by war. Following independence in 1991, Ukraine's population has experienced persistent decline due to multiple factors: mortality rates exceeding birth rates, increased emigration following the dissolution of the Soviet Union, and sharp population losses resulting from Russia's annexation of Crimea in 2014 and the conflict in Donbas. From 1991 to 2021, Ukraine's population decreased by 20%, reaching 43.8 million (Kulu et al., 2023). Following Russia's full-scale invasion in 2022, population figures declined

³ Authors' calculations.

dramatically to 37 million by 2023 (World Bank, 2023). As of July 2024, the population in territories under full Ukrainian government control stands at 31.1 million. Demographic challenges are further complicated by an aging population, with individuals aged 60 and over comprising 24.8% of the total population as of January 2022. This aging trend is exacerbated by the forced emigration of women with children (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2024b). Whilst casualty figures remain classified, recent Central Intelligence Agency data indicates that Ukraine now exhibits both the highest mortality rate globally (Central Intelligence Agency, 2024a) and the lowest birth rate (Central Intelligence Agency, 2024b).

Official records indicate 2.7 million registered persons with disabilities in Ukraine, including more than 160,000 children. However, the actual figure likely approaches the international disability prevalence rate of 16%. This would suggest that Ukraine has over 6 million people with disabilities, including 20% of the country's 11.3 million pensioners (World Health Organization, 2023).

Currently, comprehensive and precise statistical data regarding war-related disabilities remains unavailable. However, indirect indicators provide some insight into the scale of the issue. For instance, between 24 February 2022 and 31 October 2023, more than 16,100 individuals sought prosthetic services for upper and/or lower limbs from relevant government agencies (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2024b). Unofficial media reports suggest the number of war-related disabilities may be substantially higher (Cooper et al., 2023).

Whilst Ukrainian authorities acknowledge that encouraging women's return from abroad and increasing birth rates necessitates creating appropriate conditions, including suitable infrastructure (Kulu et al., 2023; Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2024b), post-war reconstruction plans appear to prioritise barrier-free space development. However, while barrier-free spaces address critical accessibility needs for people with disabilities and other mobility challenges, they do not fully encompass the broader spectrum of gender-specific requirements.

Significantly, whilst the creation of barrier-free physical space constitutes a crucial component in developing gender-equitable urban environments—particularly given that both women and men comprise mobility-challenged population groups—it is noteworthy that gender-responsive urban planning extends considerably beyond accessibility requirements for individuals with limited mobility. Indeed, it encompasses broader considerations of safety, convenience, and accessibility of urban spaces for all women and men, alongside ensuring gender-balanced representation in planning processes (Damyanovic & Zibell, 2019).

Implementation of the European Charter: Between formal adoption and practical impact

The European Charter for Equality of Women and Men in Local Life has emerged as a crucial instrument for advancing gender equality at the local level in Ukraine. As of October 2024, 87 territorial communities and two regional councils in Ukraine had adopted the Charter (Association of Ukrainian Cities, 2024). Kyiv's accession to the Charter in 2019 established formal obligations for developing and implementing specific action plans. In December 2023, the Kyiv City Council approved the Action Plan for Achieving Equality and Implementing the European Charter for Equality of Women and Men in the Life of the Territorial Community of Kyiv for 2024-2026. This plan encompasses both gender audits and accessibility assessments of specific facility categories and territories, whilst also incorporating gender analysis of passenger transport services (Kyiv City Council, 2023). However, Kyiv's experience suggests that one should exercise caution in overestimating the Charter's influence on implementing gender-responsive approaches to urban planning in Ukrainian cities at this stage.

Discussion

Gender-sensitive and gender-inclusive urban planning constitute fundamental mechanisms for achieving equality in cities, encompassing not merely physical accessibility but the integration of diverse needs and experiences across all population groups. However, within the current context of Ukraine's post-war reconstruction, amidst ongoing conflict, state institutional mechanisms predominantly emphasise barrier-free environments and physical inclusivity, driven by significant demographic shifts and a marked increase in the population with disabilities.

The European Union's support for Ukraine's reconstruction initiatives and funding priorities similarly focuses on barrier-free development and accessibility. Moreover, the EU's influence is constrained by the absence of direct legal mechanisms to enforce gender-sensitive urban planning at the local level, both within member states and candidate countries.

Nevertheless, the EU has exercised considerable influence in developing gender policies and cultural awareness within Ukrainian society, establishing robust foundations for grassroots initiatives. These bottom-up developments, including the increasing adoption of the European Charter for Equality of Women and Men in Local Life by Ukrainian municipalities, demonstrate significant potential for fostering comprehensive gender equality through local commitments, albeit without yet yielding substantial urban planning projects.

This complex interplay raises compelling questions: might these concurrent processes—post-war reconstruction, dramatic societal transformations, and European integration—create an unexpected 'window of opportunity' for implementing gender-sensitive and gender-inclusive

approaches in urban planning? Or will the immediate imperatives of creating barrier-free environments maintain precedence for decades to come? Whilst barrier-free infrastructure remains critically important for any society, particularly in post-conflict contexts, the absence of clear gender equality integration in urban planning constrains the potential for creating truly inclusive spaces.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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